

FORMING THE SPIRIT OF LOVE FOR MUSIC HERITAGE

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One of the main goals of national spirituality and cultural development is to raise the consciousness and thinking of the young generation, educate them within the requirements of aesthetic relations, and pay attention to the need to deeply study the legacy of our ancestors, that is, music and creativity.

In the upbringing of a perfect generation, especially in social life, the role and importance of music in the formation of the aesthetic relations of our youth, the role and importance of music, and the ability of the teachers to assess its effectiveness as much as possible, based on scientific research, and at the same time at the same time, the place of our nation in the history of human cultural development, its contribution to the world's spiritual treasure, the cultural and industrial wealth created by our great ancestors, the transfer of musical culture to the future generation, today this spiritual It is becoming our duty to nurture their wealth in the interests of the independence ideology in this spirit.

As we all know, the musical culture of the Uzbek people has a long historical history, professional music that glorifies its interpretation in traditional performance, a unique school of composition of our people, as well as traditional, folklore-artistic amateur music, oral creativity and other We emphasize that the riches inherent in the spiritual heritage of our people, at the level of traditional, national value, classical heritage has become one of the main criteria in the work of improving the education of the young generation. , songs and music accompanied them even on the days of joy" - they emphasized. (This information is taken from page 2 of S. Mannonov's "Uzbek Folk Music Culture Monograph").

Our traditional music and songs have always called people to faith, kindness, harmony and cooperation in our past history and in our present day. We see that at the root of such principles lies the essence of the happy services and creative products of our ancestors. In particular, the translation of the Holy Qur'an into Uzbek, the complete publication of hadiths, enjoying the works of Nasiruddin Ragbuzi, Ahmad Abu Nasr Motrudi and dozens of other great figures, the spiritual world of our great-grandfather Amir Temur. The fact that the timely use of wise teachings and deeds has mobilized all of us to do good deeds is the honor of independence itself. Of course, in order to achieve the future of a great

country, a great past, it is necessary to be intelligent, enlightened, at the same time, proud of its past, great values, nation and believe in a great future.

After all, the secondary school education system is a network aimed at acquiring primary and secondary knowledge. Therefore, every student - young people who receive their primary education in this system must try to learn the basics of spiritual and educational knowledge perfectly, relying on our national values. The level of striving for perfection of our youth leads to the achievement of perfection qualities.

According to the wisdom of our forefathers, the great figure Mir Alisher Navoi, the greatest virtue of a person is to do good and have good behavior. The second is honesty, and the third is modesty. Only when such beauty features are combined, it leads to the relationship of aesthetics - compatibility with all the beauty that happens in a person's life. Therefore, by providing education and upbringing of young people in aesthetic relations, we will focus on the formation of their spiritual and cultural needs. Of course, at the root of such factors should be the main goal in the daily creative activities of the family, school and cultural and educational centers, as well as the general public.

There is a saying in our nation that children are brought up not only by parents, but also by relatives, neighbors, and the community. At the same time, there is a saying that seven neighborhoods are responsible for one child, and it is noted that the general public is meant in this matter. We described that the role of our national music and traditional songs in improving the culture of our people and developing their worldview abilities is incomparable. The masterpieces of our national music and our traditional songs have been passed from mouth to mouth among our people since before, they were sung and performed through music, and they had a great educational value in their time. Classic tunes and songs have been the main means of improving the thinking of our youth in terms of spiritual and aesthetic aspects.

The great thinker poet Saadi Shiraz called the melody and song "food for the soul". The great Abu Ali Ibn Sina writes in the 1st book of his "Laws of Medicine": "In order to strengthen the client of a child, two things should be applied to him. One is rocking the child slowly, and the other is music and singing, which have become a habit to put him to sleep. Depending on the amount of acceptance of these two, the child's talent for education with his body and for music with his soul is formed" (S. Mannonov. The above monograph, p. 84). As you can see, we understand that the content of these words of our grandfather proves how important music is for child education. Therefore, the impressive feature of our

songs is the performer's choice of topic, the power of the performance in the content that matches the child's psyche, which has the ability to attract any person.

If we try to analyze the characteristics of the effectiveness of traditional songs, we will see that they are related to all aspects of human life, social events and events. In all periods of social life, people have tried to create a creative mobilization to raise their views to a certain extent, enjoying musical culture and art. Spiritual perfection has been an ancient, universal value of our people, and it is still bearing its fruit today. Music is a great blessing, because it is recognized as a means of spiritual connection to the human body. A song is a poetic text with a certain content, meaning and essence, and a work is a poetic text. It provides poetic harmony of the work. This harmony, as an integral part of the education of young people, is of great importance in forming their musical aesthetic culture and spiritual world.

Effective and appropriate use of folk music traditions in the education of young people is becoming an educational issue more than ever today. As a result of the "internationalization" of Uzbek music, there are cases of deviation from the use of Uzbek folk music traditions.

A melody is an expression of the royal mood of the human soul. The idea and imagination of a musical work first appears in the imagination, and then comes to life due to the performance and turns into a specific melody. The life of a melody is very short: as soon as it appears, it escapes and disappears in an instant. But an impressive sound, a melody leaves a mark in the heart of the listener, arouses pleasure and invites to aspire to this pleasant state again.

One of the simplest ways to preserve the pleasure of music is to share the situation that has arisen in the heart with close souls. If the first melody of the melody is accepted, if it has an effect without remaining indifferent, it will arouse the desire to continue this pleasure. In this state of mind, the hearts of the performer and the listener are connected, and they begin to feed on the melody. From such a connection of emotions, a harmonious musical process is created, in which the performer becomes a creator - creators, and the listener becomes his fan. This pleasure develops more and more, the melodies are combined, turn into melodic sentences, and they, in turn, turn into larger compounds. In this way, a full-length melody emerges from primary beat and tone particles. Their combination creates great works. Therefore, music is not just a complex of sounds, but rather a coordinated system of pitches and methods. Most importantly, a melody is a meaning expressed through pleasant

sounds. Meaningless sound is nothing more than noise. In particular, the important melodies that have become a tradition are based on such deep meanings that the people's memory preserves them as classic works. The unique family of music known as "People's Music" has also grown up in this way.

In the era of Timurids, there was a concept of "ilmi advor" (multiplicity of the advor circle) and it meant the commonality of theoretical and practical foundations of melody, vase, and poetry. The art of folk music has a rich mentality that comes from the traditional way of life, moral norms, and the spiritual nourishment of music, the worldviews that encourage people to perfection.

In short, folk music is a world of musical imagination and ideas that are difficult to express in words. Its arrowroots receive nourishment equally from the sources of mind and emotions. It is a joint artistic process that incorporates the arts of music, poetry and dance. The poetry and dance contained in it are not just secondary means that come in the place of decoration or filling. On the contrary, in it, melody and melody, words and poetry, dance and movement are closely connected and combined into a single artistic form. Despite such versatility, a work of art is, first of all, music, melody. It is manifested in the form of a musical factor, from a small film to a whole large series.

The style of musical creativity is of great importance for the development of musical knowledge, research and creativity in children. This method is performed with creative practices such as accompanying the teacher's performance by tapping the circle, "conducting" the class performance, finding movements that match the melody, singing a melody to a piece of poetry, and "composing". This method is especially important to pay attention to talented students in the class and to satisfy their artistic needs.

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